

ISic0723

I.Sicily inscription 0723

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2006.04; 2013.10.04

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Euryelos (?)

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 104858

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. C(aius) Norb[anus---f(ilius)---n(epos)Balbus]
2. anno [extremopraeturae]
3. [Q(uintus)A]nic[ius---]
4. [quaestorpropr(aetore)---]
5. [viasin]cl[inatasetangustasa]
6. Syracus[s]isadAcrasvorsus]
7. praeter[missisinviissemitis]
8. et ab Ac[risadAgrigentum]
9. vorsus a[diectispontibus]
10. refe[cerunt][latores]

Apparatus

Text of Manganaro 1989 including restorations

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175777

EDCS 24700261

Bibliography

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